

EDUTAINMENT AS A NEW TREND IN LANGUAGE ACQUISITION**Sobirova Asilabonu Aziz kizi**

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Abstract: In this article, global trends in language learning in the 21st century are given and one of them how “Edutainment” helps school and university students are discussed. Edutainment technology was introduced into the process of teaching English to students based on several electronic resources and gadgets. The differences between edutainment tools for young and teenage students are given as an example of English language teaching. Interactive ways of classroom management and new teaching methods instead of simple traditional lessons are considered as more helpful ones for students. In order to avoid boring lessons, young scholars and pedagogics are recommending interactive ways of language skills.

Keywords: Kahoot, Word wall, Ispring suit, trend, creativity, multimedia, gamification, media tools.

‘Every student can learn, just not on the same day, or the same way.’

–George Evans.

Communication between people with different languages throughout the world is one of the main features of this modern world. In this regard, teaching and learning foreign languages plays a crucial role. In our country organizing and creating several teaching content and learning strategies in a modern way are suggested. In addition to this, there are a number of existing trends that provide very good solutions to educational tasks and learning a new foreign language. In this century the need for interesting and beneficial activities is increasing day by day, as the more interesting the learning environment is, the better child’s learning improves. Pedagogical science has a plethora of innovative and creative ideas, techniques, methods, tips, strategies, and technologies which are the types of modern education. “Edutainment” as a meta-subject is one of

these trends that helps to develop student's language competence. Initially, the components of this word should be assumed, which came from the merger of the English words "education" and "entertainment". The term edutainment was first introduced by the Walt Disney Company which used it in its series „Real Adventures”. Education is teaching a particular subject on a specific topic. Entertainment is a representation and pastime which gives people a sense of pleasure. The combination of these words gives different meanings that learning and teaching through entertainment. The youth is so intelligent and initiative that only simple teaching is not adequate for them. It is not only devoted to primary children, but also students at university. It is already impossible to imagine modern learning and communication without multimedia tools and social media such as audio, video games, television programs, music, movies, and websites. Changing traditional classes, lectures, seminars, and master classes is the beginning of modern forms of entertainment technology. The future of edutainment is continuing trend [1]. Educators should not only teach, but entertain via edutainment technologies which bring students better, and quicker integration. According to some researchers, edutainment is the balance between information, multimedia products, psychological tips and modern technologies [2]. There is nothing more natural for students than learning about the world through playing and experiencing based on reality. Z and Alpha generation children have been nicknamed as “screenagers”, because they are living in the atmosphere of electronic gadgets. The methods used in gamification help to ensure full immersion and engagement during lessons. For primary school students mini-games, comics, and reward systems are types of strategies that capture more children's attention [3]. Conventional ways of assessing language acquisition are not adequate today, language learning is a more complicated, nonlinear, and communicative endeavor. Over the past 20 years, there has been a worldwide movement in the techniques of the education system, most scholars are initiating learning a new language as a second or more [4]. Gamification is a good tool, that's why more and more online educative games emerge where players have to solve language tasks and can receive rewards, if they win. Also, experts find video learning insightful and creative. For instance, video tutorials with animations are the best ways for audience learning [5]. The followings are edutainment tools that are beneficial for educators:

Puzzles, Kahoot, Word wall, Ispring suit and others [6].

Educational technology tools appeal greatly to language instructors because of their contribution to students' active participation and maximizing positive learning outcomes (Mohammad Reza Ahmadi.2018) [7]. Modern types of language teaching and learning technologies include language labs, digitalization, multimedia devices, mobile phones, audio/visual multimedia content, Ed-Tech solutions, and social media which can facilitate faster and more comprehensive language progression.

1-picture.

“ As marketers, we need to make sure we are not only educating but also entertaining so that we can hold the attention of our customers and prospects. ”

2-picture.

These were all for school students' materials that intend to be both educational and enjoyable. Catching young learners' attention with vivid colors and step-by-step strategies is not always easy for teachers and pedagogics.

Education is an ongoing process and is considered in various forms. Involving students is one of the important parts of the lesson for teachers, as Benjamin Franklin said: „Tell me and I forget. Teach me and I remember. Involve me and I learn”. There is a huge difference between edutainment tools that are managed for high schools and universities and primary schools. For instance, high school students are not engaged with games and toys, visa versa young learners are more keen on watching comics and cartoons. Listening to beneficial radio and podcasts, and watching movies in targeted language are recommended for them [8]. Due to the digitalization of society, there is a strong demand for the application of teaching and learning tool for effective

language acquisition. Currently, many interactive online platforms that keep students' interest and increase their motivation [9].

3-picture.

4-picture.

In order to make students practice more for their future professions, organizing lessons in a more lively environment would be the best practice, firstly. Secondly, the class topic would be learned with interest and deep. Museums and public access areas, parks, companies, farms, schools, and kindergartens are the best places to go with peers and experts [10].

The world is changing rapidly, and how we learn is also. Students are as curious as they have to be guided and mentored. The young generation is experiencing the world with technology, so today's language classrooms are vastly different, and new teaching methods and trends like edutainment are increasing and being utilized day by day. Personally, I would recommend the usage of e-recourses and media tools for language acquisition in the modern education system.

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